
The Advantages Of A Flipped Classroom For Students' Speaking Skills: A Systematic Review

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to provide a systematic review of the advantages of a flipped classroom for students' speaking skills. Before carrying out this systematic review for the methodology, the researcher searched the publication data on Google Scholar for 2018-2023 regarding flipped classroom and speaking. It was found 97 data, which were analyzed through the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) to 28 data. Based on the findings, the advantages of a flipped classroom for students' speaking skills are engagement, confidence, motivation, improvement, and self-paced learning. The frequency of these studies is 9 engagements, 11 confidences, 10 motivations, 26 improvements, and 7 self-paced learnings. It indicates that the majority of research discuss about the improvement in students' speaking skills in flipped classrooms. On the other hand, the flipped classroom contributed positively to the students' speaking skills. Furthermore, some suggestions will help to educators and future scholars.

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INTRODUCTION

Rapid technology has had a profound impact on pedagogy, particularly language learning and teaching. In elementary, middle school, and university settings, technology-based learning is already available in enhanced, blended, and fully online forms. Technology is extensively used in pedagogical practices such as blended learning ((Abdullah et al., (2019); Delialioglu and Yildirim (2007); Grgurovic (2010).). The transition from traditional to blended learning has been gradually opening the door for more adaptable teaching and learning models like the flipped classroom model.

In Indonesia, the majority of EFL students lack confidence when they come to speaking English either in front of others or in a class. Although they have studied English, they do not have idea how to use it. They do not have a lot of opportunities to practice speaking English, so their vocabulary is still limited. Moreover, poor pronunciation makes it hard for them to understand sentences. The students believe that

their teachers do not encourage them or give them advice on how to get better at speaking because in teaching English, teachers still use traditional methods in and focus more on grammar. This implies that teachers need to use technology efficiently. Therefore, it is important for teachers to use the flipped classroom to enhance students' speaking.

Theoretically, the flip model develops from F-L-I-P, which describes a flexible environment, learning culture, intentional content, and professional educators by Pratiwi et al., (2021). A flipped classroom is a situation in which an activity “which is traditionally done in class is now done at home, and that which is traditionally done as homework is now completed in class” according to Demir & Mirzaie, (2023). A flipped classroom offers several benefits. Students will spend less time in class listening to lectures since they can attend the lectures on video at home. Activities in the classroom will be used to solve problems and have discussions. The video lecture students watch at home in a flipped classroom takes the place of live instruction in the classroom, and while in the classroom, they engage in more involved and dynamic activities like teamwork according to Kristyowatia et al., (2023); S. Cohen & K., (2013).

However, some research has revealed the implementation's shortcomings with regard to the flipped classroom model. The initial investigation was carried out by Jakob (2022) to improve students' speaking skills through the flipped classroom model. The findings indicated that students' motivation to learn English had increased. The rise in speaking skill average value in the first cycle (75.6), second cycle (79.23), and third cycle (89.2) was the evidence of this. This led to the conclusion that teaching English speaking using the flipped classroom model was a learning strategy that could be consulted when developing the speaking skill learning process. The second finding was carried out by Anwar (2022) about the students' perceptions of the flipped classroom in teaching speaking skill. The finding showed that students thought the flipped classroom strategy was intriguing, and then they could comprehend the process. In addition, the flipped classroom strategy improved the engagement.

Despite so many studies about flipped classrooms, there is still a lack of systematic review methods focused on speaking skills because most of the studies are not concerned with a specific language. Instead, they are in general areas such as ELT. Therefore, this systematic literature review aims to provide a systematic review about the advantages of Flipped classroom in students' speaking skill. Meanwhile, the research question is "What are the advantages of a flipped classroom in students' speaking skill?"

METHOD

This systematic literature search was based on the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA). A systematic literature review (SLR) involves selecting, identifying, and evaluating research findings to answer a clearly stated research question. As this article aims to provide a systematic review of the advantages of a flipped classroom for students' speaking skills. In the Publish or Perish database. There are four phases : identification phase, screening phase, eligibility phase, and including phase.

In the identification phase, the researcher was searching on publish and perish the database from Google Scholar. The articles need to be published between 2018 and 2023. The total amount of data in Google Scholar is 97 articles. The database is a free and accessible search engine that includes most peer-reviewed literature across an array of disciplines. The articles were identified through the related keywords based on the search engines “flipped learning and speaking skills” and “flipped classroom and speaking skills.” Next, the articles underwent the inclusion and exclusion criteria to ensure that the selected articles aligned with the framework needed for the review, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The inclusion and exclusion criteria

No	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
1.	Journal Articles	Book chapters, book, proceedings, review and meta analysis
2.	Article published between 2018 till 2023	Articles that were not published between 2018 till 2023

3.	Sample of respondents from various level of education	Articles that are not published in English language, not Arabic or Spanish
4.	Sample of respondents from various level of education	
5.	The researches selected in various country	

In the screening phase, the researcher was screening the titles and abstracts of the publications to further filter them. Because the titles matched the search term, they were filtered. Next, each article's abstract was quickly skimmed and scanned. While choosing the articles based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria, the abstracts of the publications were reviewed. The total amount of data in Google Scholar is 55 articles.

In the eligibility phase, The articles must comply with Table 1's inclusion and exclusion criteria. Restricted articles were not included in the full text download that qualified for download. Stated differently, the publications that are chosen should address the research questions. Therefore, it was crucial to consider both inclusion and exclusion criteria when creating a high-caliber study. The total amount of data in Google Scholar is 42 articles.

In the exclusion phase, the remaining research papers were eliminated from this study after the eligibility phase articles were reviewed. Articles that were not published in English, including book chapters, books, proceedings, reviews, and meta-analyses, were omitted. Not published articles between 2018 and 2023 were also not included. This procedure is crucial since it's the final stage in streamlining the search for pertinent flipped classroom articles that improve speaking abilities. The total amount of data in Google Scholar is 28 articles. The PRISMA flow chart in Figure 1 provides a summary of the information gleaned from the search process. The details are summarized from the searching process using PRISMA flow chart in Figure 1.

There were 28 articles selected based on the criteria of a flipped classroom in terms of students' speaking skills. The articles were divided into three research methods. There are a total of 12 mixed-method studies: 6 quantitative studies, 4 qualitative studies, 4 semi-qualitative studies, 1 experimental method, and 1 efficient method.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

There are 97 articles from the years 2018 to 2023 located in the Google Scholar databases in Publish and Perish. The search terms were used to filter and gather any papers that looked into the connection between speaking skill improvement and flipped learning. After that, the results were filtered, and 55 articles were disqualified after the title and abstract were checked. Then, 14 publications that were review papers, Meta analyses, and bibliometric studies were eliminated because they lacked full text access. Ultimately, 28 papers were chosen for this review based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. An overview of the research studies, the nation, the research methodology, and the number of study participants is provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Characteristics of Research Studies

No	Author(s)	Country	Research Method	Research Participants
1.	Mie-Rong Alice Chen, Gwo Jen Hwang (2019)	Taiwan	Quantitative	72 College Students
2.	Damar Isti Pratiwi, U. Ubaedillah, Armyta Puspitasari, Teguh Arifianto (2021)	Indonesia	Quantitative	48 Students
3.	Imam Sudarmaji, Ariskha Ananda Amaliyah Anwar, Agus Mulyana (2021)	Indonesia	Mixed Method	35 High School Students
4.	Sabahattin Yesilcinar (2019)	Turkey	Mixed Method	22 EFL Learners
5.	Mohamad Yahya Abdullah (2021)	Oman	Mixed Method	27 Undergraduate Student
6.	Marady Phoeun, Supanee Sengsri (2021)	Cambodia	Mixed Method	21 Pre-intermediate Level
7.	Mohamad Yahya Abdullah, Supyan Hussin, Kemboja Ismail (2019)	Oman	Mixed Method	27 Students
8.	Gihan Sidky (2019)	Egypt	Qualitative	38 Secondary Stage
9.	Dyah Kristyowatia, Jordy Satria Widodoh Resty, Widya Kurniasaric (2023)	Indonesia	Semi-Qualitative	30 University Student
10.	Hebah Asaad Hamza Sheerah, Meenakshi Sharma Yadav (2022)	Saudi Arabia	Quantitative	32 University Student
11.	Demir, C & Mirzaie, H. (2023)	Iran	Quantitative	47 Intermediate EFL Students
12.	Necati SONMEZ (2020)	Turkey	Quantitative	8 University Students
13.	JC Jakob, A Asrifan (2022)	Indonesia	Semi-Qualitative	78 College Students
14.	Isti Rohmawati, Choiril Anwar (2022)	Indonesia	Qualitative	23 High School Students
15.	Titik Rahayu, Imam Mudofir, Alief Sutanto (2019)	Indonesia	Semi-Qualitative	22 College Students
16.	Boriboon Choathamdeand Patthaporn Langprayoon (2022)	Indonesia	Mixed Method	33 Undergraduate Students
17.	Maedeh Davari, Behdokht Mall-Amari (2022)	Iran	Mixed Method	32 Intermediate Students
18.	Jitpanat Suwanthep, Shuangjiang L (2018)	Thailand	Mixed Method	32 Intermediate Students
19.	Taufik, Widyastuti Purbani (2019)	Indonesia	Semi-Qualitative	19 Vocational High School
20.	Thawinee Ponsa, Adinda Tasya, Wanida Simpol (2021)	Indonesia	Mixed Method	14 Primary Students
21.	Ni Made Kristianti, Luh Putu Artini, I.G.A Lokita Purnamika Utami (2023)	Indonesia	Quantitative	61 High School Students
22.	Abd. Rahman, Sahril, Muhaiminah Akib (2023)	Indonesia	Mixed Method	41 College Students
23.	Marlisha Nisa Fatur Rahma, Mansyur Srisudarso, Fauzi Miftakh (2023)	Indonesia	Qualitative	3 Primary Students
24.	Reflianto, Farida Arinani (2018)	Indonesia	Quantitative	56 High School Students
25.	Wafa Achkou (2018)	Lithuania	Qualitative	6 College Students
26.	Dilini Hemali, Gavithri Ganepola (2023)	Sri Lanka	Mixed Method	120 College Students
27.	Truong Hoang Hau (2022)	Vietnam	Mixed Method	30 College Students and 2 Lectures
28.	Ajang Spriyono, Agung Wicaksono, Khoriyah (2020)	Indonesia	Qualitative	25 High School Students

Comparing the level of research participants, the most studies concentrated on colleges or universities (9 studies), followed by high school students (6 studies), undergraduate students (3 studies), intermediate students (3 studies), students (2 studies), primary students (2 studies), lectures (2 studies), and one study on secondary stages. For this figure identification about level of research participants. That is figure 1.

Figure 1. Level of Research Participants

Furthermore, there were 28 articles identified with the advantages in students' speaking skill. it consist of five common advantages identified from the articles which are engagement (Mie Rong, Alice Chen, Gwo Jen Hwang, 2019; Mohamad Yahya Abdullah, 2021; Marady Phoeun, Supanee Sengsri, 2021; Dyah Kristyowatia, Jordy Satria Widodob, Resty Widya Kurniasaric, 2023; Necati, 2020; Isti Rohmawati, Choiril Anwar, 2022; Titik Rahayu, Imam Mudofir, Alief Sutanto, 2019; Maedeh Davari, Behdokht Mall Amiri, 2022; Ni Made Kristianti, Luh Putu Artini, I.G.A Lokita Purnamika Utami, 2023; Reflianto, Farida Ariani, 2018; Dilini Hemali, Gavithri Ganepola, 2023; Ajang Spriyono, Agung Wicaksono, Khoriyah, 2022); Confident (Imam Sudarmaji, Ariskha Ananda Amaliyah Anwar, Agus Mulyana, 2021; Mohamad Yahya Abdullah, 2021; Marady Phoeun, Supanee Sengsri, 2021; Gihan Sidky; 2019; Hebah Asaad Hamza Sheerah, Meenakshi Sharma Yadav, 2022; Necati, 2020; Isti Rohmawati, Choiril Anwar, 2022; Jitpanat Suwanthep, Shuangjiang, 2018; Abd. Rahman, Sahril, Muhaiminah Akib, 2023; Wafa Achkou, 2018; Truong Hoang Hau, 2022); Motivation (Mie Rong, Alice Chen, Gwo Jen Hwang, 2019; Damar Isti Pratiwi, U. Ubaedillah, Armyta Puspitasari, Teguh Arifianto, 2021; Sabahattin, 2021; Mohamad Yahya Abdullah, 2021; Mohamad Yahya Abdullah, Supyan Hussin, Kemboja Ismail, 2019; Demir C, Mirzae H, 2023; JC Jakob, A Asrifan, 2022; Maedeh Davari, Behdokht Mall Amiri, 2022; Ni Made Kristianti, Luh Putu Artini, I.G.A Lokita Purnamika Utami, 2023; Abd. Rahman, Sahril, Muhaimah Akib, 2023; Marlisha Nisa Fatur Rahma, Mansyur Srisudarso, Fauzi Miftakh, 2023; Reflianto, Farida Ariani, 2018; Ajang Spriyono, Agung Wicaksono, Khoriyah, 2022); Improvement (Mie Rong, Alice Chen, Gwo Jen Hwang, 2019; Damar Isti Pratiwi, U. Ubaedillah, Armyta Puspitasari, Teguh Arifianto, 2021; Imam Sudarmaji, Ariskha Ananda Amaliyah Anwar, Agus Mulyana, 2021; Sabahattin, 2021; Marady Phoeun, Supanee Sengsri, 2021; Mohamad Yahya Abdullah, Supyan Hussin, Kemboja Ismail, 2019; Gihan Sidky; 2019; Dyah Kristyowatia, Jordy Satria Widodob, Resty Widya Kurniasaric, 2023; Demir C, Mirzae H, 2023; Necati, 2020; JC Jakob, A Asrifan, 2022; Titik Rahayu, Imam Mudofir, Alief Sutanto, 2019; Boriboon Chobthamdeeand Patthaporn Langprayoon, 2022; Jitpanat Suwanthep, Shuangjiang, 2018; Taufik, Widyastuti Purbani, 2019; Thawinee Ponsa1 , Adinda Tasya2 , Wanida Simpol, 2021; Ni Made Kristianti, Luh Putu Artini, I.G.A Lokita Purnamika Utami, 2023; Abd. Rahman, Sahril, Muhaimah Akib, 2023; Marlisha Nisa Fatur Rahma, Mansyur Srisudarso, Fauzi Miftakh, 2023; Reflianto, Farida Ariani, 2018; Wafa Achkou, 2018; Dilini Hemali, Gavithri Ganepola, 2023; Truong Hoang Hau, 2022; Ajang Spriyono, Agung Wicaksono, Khoriyah, 2022); and self-paced learning (Damar Isti Pratiwi, U. Ubaedillah, Armyta Puspitasari, Teguh Arifianto, 2021; Imam Sudarmaji, Ariskha Ananda Amaliyah Anwar, Agus Mulyana, 2021; Sabahattin, 2021; Sabahattin, 2021; Gihan Sidky; 2019; Boriboon Chobthamdeeand Patthaporn Langprayoon, 2022; Jitpanat Suwanthep, Shuangjiang, 2018; Truong Hoang Hau, 2022).

The results were tabulated in Table 3.

Table 3. Frequency Previous Studies

No	Author(s)	Engagement	Confidence	Motivation	Improvement	Self-Paced Learning
1.	Mie-Rong Alice Chen, Gwo Jen Hwang (2019)	v		v	v	
2.	Damar Isti Pratiwi, U. Ubaedillah, Armyta Puspitasari, Teguh Arifianto (2021)			v	v	v
3.	Imam Sudarmaji, Ariskha Ananda Amaliyah Anwar, Agus Mulyana (2021)		v		v	v
4.	Sabahattin Yesilcinar (2019)			v	v	v
5.	Mohamad Yahya Abdullah (2021)	v	v	v		
6.	Marady Phoeun, Supanee Sengsri (2021)	v	v		v	
7.	Mohamad Yahya Abdullah, Supyan Hussin, Kemboja Ismail (2019)			v	v	
8.	Gihan Sidky (2019)		v		v	v
9.	Dyah Kristyowatia, Jordy Satria Widodoh Resty, Widya Kurniasaric (2023)	v			v	
10.	Hebah Asaad Hamza Sheerah, Meenakshi Sharma Yadav (2022)		v			
11.	Demir, C & Mirzaie, H. (2023)			v	v	
12.	Necati SONMEZ (2020)	v	v		v	
13.	JC Jakob, A Asrifan (2022)			v	v	
14.	Isti Rohmawati, Choiril Anwar (2022)	v	v			
15.	Titik Rahayu, Imam Mudofir, Alief Sutanto (2019)	v			v	
16.	Boriboon Chothamdeeand Patthaporn Langprayoon (2022)				v	v
17.	Maedeh Davari, Behdokht Mall-Amari (2022)	v		v		
18.	Jitpanat Suwanthep, Shuangjiang L (2018)		v		v	v
19.	Taufik, Widyastuti Purbani (2019)				v	
20.	Thawinee Ponsa, Adinda Tasya, Wanida Simpol (2021)				v	
21.	Ni Made Kristianti, Luh Putu Artini, I.G.A Lokita Purnamika Utami (2023)	v		v	v	
22.	Abd. Rahman, Sahril, Muhaiminah Akib (2023)		v	v	v	
23.	Marlisha Nisa Fatur Rahma, Mansyur Srisudarso, Fauzi Miftakh (2023)			v	v	
24.	Reflianto, Farida Arinani (2018)	v		v	v	
25.	Wafa Achkou (2018)		v		v	
26.	Dilini Hemali, Gavithri Ganepola (2023)	v			v	
27.	Truong Hoang Hau (2022)		v		v	v
28.	Ajang Spriyono, Agung Wicaksono, Khoriyah (2020)	v		v	v	

Based on the table above, it can be concluded that there are five advantages that researchers found based on the frequency of previous studies. It consists of nine engagements, 11 confidences, 10 motivations, 26 improvements, and seven self-paced learning sessions. The table showed that the majority of research discussions about the improvement of students' speaking skills in flipped classrooms indicate that flipped classrooms provide positive feedback for students' speaking skills.

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This part will focus on the advantages of the flipped classroom method in improving speaking skills. There are five primary advantages of flipped learning methods in improving speaking skills; engagement, confidence, motivation, and improvement and self-paced learning.

There are a total of 9 researches that highlight that the flipped classroom method can result in the student's active engagement. This approach has benefited student learning outcomes. In flipped classroom, students view and study material at their own pace and respond to content during group time. This situation created learner engagement beyond the usual non-participatory classroom tasks (Mei-Rong, 2019). Students can also base their responses on understanding concepts that they have developed. Flipped classroom methods are also effective in terms of encouraging students' involvement in the learning process. This method gives students chances to talk, share and express themselves which made them used to it and build their confidence (M. Phoen, 2021)

In the study conducted by Maedah Davari (2022), it was found that the method was useful in terms of student's engagement in the class. It is proven by the students having more time to ask for clarification during class. Unlike conventional methods, the students become more engaged by this method.

A total of 11 studies discussed students' confidence in speaking skills. The significant rise in flipped learning has not only shifted the traditional teaching and learning methods, but has also increased pupils' interaction level with their teacher and peers. More time is allocated for student interaction with peers and instructors both in and out of class hours through the flipped learning environment. JC Jacob (2022) in his study stated that the method succeeded in improving students' speaking skills where the students watched and learned videos at home sent by the teacher. The students then were capable of holding group discussions actively and well. Additionally, Gihan Sidky (2019) pointed out that after applying this method for a year, this method showed its efficacy in improving student's confidence in speaking English. The students are able to express their ideas fluently without any hesitation and are able to pronounce words better.

From a motivation perspective, a total of 10 studies on improving students' speaking skills through a flipped learning approach were discussed. Motivation plays an important role in helping students improve their speaking skills.

A study by Jacob (2022) shows that language learning using a flipped learning approach depends on the motivation level of the students. This has a direct impact on practice, as students can review learning materials to increase their engagement in learning and motivation to speak up. Flipped learning increases student engagement through active learning. Students actively participate in activities and take responsibility for their own learning. This leaves more time to learn new things and increase student participation (Damar, 2021; Abdullah, 2020; Maedah & Behdokht, 2020; Rahman & Sahril, 2023)

According to Yahya (2019), The application of flipped learning methods was found motivating, inspiring, peaceful and comfortable for learners. It happens because it helps the students support each other's weaknesses and shortcomings as they cooperate and share together. As autonomy increases, students' motivation for flipped learning also increases. Lack of motivation, fear of speaking, and limited resources were some challenges encountered in the flipped learning approach. Therefore, with continued motivation, students will feel confident and able to converse freely with others.

A total of 26 studies talks over the level of improvement perspective in improving speaking skills (Ajang Spriyono, 2022; Wafa Achkou, 2018; Reflianto 2018; Ni Made Kristianti, 2023, and another 22 the studies) These studies showed that compared to traditional classrooms, flipped classrooms improved student performance and significantly improved speaking skills. Flipped classrooms have become a popular teaching and learning method to replace traditional classrooms. Flipped students achieve better grades and speak the language more confidently. The reviewed studies also showed that it has great potential to improve students' academic performance and help them improve their language learning and speaking practice. Overall, students in flipped classrooms outperformed students in non-flipped classrooms in language learning. There is little research on using web tools and platforms to improve student performance through flipped learning approaches. The results showed that the flipped classroom model improved the language proficiency and proficiency level of adult learners.

As the demand for flipped classrooms increases in educational institutions, it becomes more important to understand aspects of students' self-paced learning in this environment, as many studies have

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shown that self-regulation is important in flipped learning environments. It has become a total of 7 out of 28 studies discussing the benefits of self-regulated learning in improving speaking skills. These papers demonstrated that flipped learning promotes high levels of self-regulation in students. Students were able to learn and practice communication at their own pace. As a result, students began to actively participate in class. Furthermore, students who demonstrated strong self-regulation strategies perceived reversals more positively in their perceptions of language proficiency. Teachers using the flipped learning approach must train students to adjust their learning behavior while speaking the language. Therefore, this can be a useful objective for students to adjust their study habits and learning styles to match the reverse approach.

Extensive research has shown that students understand and respond positively to lesson content through flipped classroom activities. Students were able to adjust their learning behavior by watching recorded lessons and videos at their own pace. However, he also claimed that some of his YouTube videos are not suitable for students because they are not accustomed to the speaker's accent, putting an additional burden on teachers to modify the material. In relation to the technical specifications of the learning videos, teachers must have technical knowledge regarding the use of devices and settings. We strongly recommend that educators receive appropriate training in adapting technology to second language learning. Therefore, technical knowledge helps educators become experts in providing better speaking assignments to their students.

Application of this method is ideal for today's student-centered learning environments (Dyah, 2022). This represents an important aspect of the learning process in which the teacher is a facilitator rather than a source of learning, allowing students to discover themselves independently and develop their abilities.

CONCLUSION

This systematic literature review analyzed 28 data points on flipped learning approaches to improving speaking skills and found that the flipped learning approach has numerous advantages, including engagement, confidence, motivation, improvement, and self-paced learning. The frequency of these studies is 9 engagements, 11 confidences, 10 motivations, 26 improvements, and 7 self-paced learnings. It indicates that the majority of research discusses the improvement in students' speaking skills in flipped classrooms. A flipped classroom also promotes flexibility to improve the speaking skills of both teachers and learners at different levels. Learners take responsibility for their own learning, collaborate with each other, and exchange ideas both inside and outside the classroom. This increase speaking opportunities and promotes active learning when learning a language. There is no denying that the flipped learning approach fosters a more comfortable and appropriate learning environment for learning speaking skills. Therefore, this review provides an opportunity for teachers to adopt this flipped learning approach after the implementation of blended learning to maintain the teaching and learning process in teaching speaking skills.

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